

**A METADISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE REVIEW SECTION IN
MPHIL ENGLISH LINGUISTICS THESES: A CASE STUDY OF ISLAMIA
COLLEGE UNIVERISTY PESHAWAR PAKISTAN**

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Abstract: *This paper examines the use of metadiscourse markers in literature review sections of MPhil English Linguistics theses submitted to Islamia College Peshawar. Utilizing a mixed-method convergent parallel design, the research employed Ken Hyland's (2005) metadiscourse framework and Swales' CARS model (1990) to analyze rhetorical structure and metadiscourse strategy. The data was first analyzed using textual analysis as per the integrated model, followed by the quantification of metadiscourse markers used by research scholars in their literature reviews. The findings revealed significant variation in the use of interactive and interactional metadiscourse markers across the selected samples. Interactive markers such as IA-1 and IA-4 were frequently employed to enhance coherence, while certain samples underutilized these features. In contrast, interactional markers, particularly IR-1 and IR-4, were inconsistently applied, which affects reader's engagement and academic stance of researcher. The study also identified structural inconsistencies in the application of Swales' CARS model, particularly in Move 2, which was underdeveloped in some samples. The findings support previous literature, confirming that Pakistani ESL scholars tend to rely more on interactive than interactional markers. Based on the results, this case study suggests improved literature review writing training and discourse-focused feedback from supervisors to refine metadiscourse use in literature review writing. Further research with expanded dataset is highly recommended to explore*

Keywords: Metadiscourse Markers Analysis, Literature Review Writing in MPhil English Linguistics Theses, Swales' CARS model (1990), Ken Hyland's Metadiscourse Model (2005), ESL Academic and Research Writing

Introduction

The literature review section is the central component in thesis writing that sets ground for a research work by identifying gaps in existent literature. Unfortunately, literature review is often overlooked as a poor relation to a research work due to which research scholars face challenges in writing a well articulated literature review, because they fail to understand the very essence and requirement of this

section in research writing (Steward, 2004). Therefore many beginner graduate research scholars in general and English as a second language (ESL) in particular find it difficult to write a well-structured and organized literature review. For instance, Boote and Beile (2005) write that literature review in MPhil thesis is poorly conceptualized, merely paraphrased, and poorly written with unsupported claims that ultimately lead to its poor presentation. However, Swales and Feak (2012) in their seminal work on genre analysis labels literature review as a distinctive genre of academic writing having its one convention, norms, and expectations comprising three moves. He argues that the demand of this genre is to create a research space by establishing: a research territory (move 1), establishing a research niche (move 2), occupying the niche (move 3), and further comprising of three steps in each move (Swales & Feak 2012). However, literature reviews are frequently reported for overreliance on summary and description, poor critical evaluation of the existent literature, and its failure to engage with relevant literature (Hyland, 2005; Belcher, 2009). Moreover, Swales and Feak (2012) emphasize that literature reviews should not merely "summarize and describe" but must contribute in creating a research space (CARS) followed by the effective synthesis of literature review with proper citation arranged in chronological order to coherently communicate different voices and narratives in a convincing manner. Literature review as a genre plays a significant role in establishing the research niche and has specific structural and linguistic features, including critical evaluation, synthesis, self positioning of the author, and gap formulation (Bhatia, 2017). It is important to note that when graduate scholars write literature review, they are not just summarizing existing research. They are also shaping their own identity as researchers (Badenhorst, 2019, p. 263). By engaging with previous studies, they demonstrate their expertise and contribute to their reputation in the academic community. This professional identity of a researcher is established during an interpersonal communication through metadiscourse markers that the researcher uses to guide the reader. These metadiscourse markers are highly important for the purpose of what Deborah Tannen (1989) calls 'conversationalization' in written communication, which is to bring coherence fluency in the text, and to establish rapport with the reader. The concept of metadiscourse proposed by Ken Hyland (2005) has been especially helpful in the analysis of metadiscourse in academic writing because it broadens the field's focus from how texts depict the outside world to how they interact with readers on an interpersonal level. To clarify, it reveals the fact that researchers not only produce texts representative of an outer reality, but use language to credibly represent them by locating themselves in their research work. Research on literature review writing practices shows that the researchers have normally worked on different aspects of literature review by relying on secondary sources of data like exploring challenges, opinions, issues, etc, but have most often overlooked how the scholars' actual literature review—which after refinement and evaluation becomes the most primary, and reliable source of data—is structured and synthesized. Continuing within this "keystone genre" of thesis writing, using Ken Hyland's (2005) interpersonal model of metadiscourse backed by the seminal work of Swales's on genre analysis and his CARS model, this case study intends to explore literature review writing practices at Islamia College University Peshawar focusing on MPhil English linguistics graduate research scholars to analyze the literature review section in their theses. This model reflects on interactive and interactional discourse markers normally used by research scholars throughout their research work, especially in their literature review section when creating a research space (CARS) and synthesizing literature review which potentially affect the depth and clarity of their work. By examining the linguistic and structural characteristics of literature reviews in MPhil English Linguistics theses, this research contributes to understanding of how research scholars of Islamia College University Peshawar use language (metadiscourse) and how they structure (CARS) their literature reviews. This study therefore provides a comprehensive picture of literature review where Swale's CARS model provides the structural framework and Ken Hyland (2005) a linguistic tool to get an in-depth understanding.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is also labelled as "Cinderella" of research work, because it is overlooked as poor relation to a research, or insignificant, but it is a compulsory prelude to a research work (Steward, 2004). However, a sound literature review is much crucial as it extracts new ideas from published works by summarizing and synthesizing them. Jaroongkhongdach (2013) argues that synthesizing quality literature review is crucial for graduate studies and in research publications. However, many beginner

researchers and graduate students find it difficult to write a good literature review. For instance, Boote and Beile (2005) found that the literature review in the MPhil thesis is poorly conceptualized and written. Similarly, Onwuegbuzie and Daniel (2005) report that literature reviews of research work are underdeveloped with unsupported claims ultimately leading to poor presentation of literature review. These problems are seen as common in different disciplines and fields of study including social sciences (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2008; Zorn & Campbell, 2006). Literature reviews can be found everywhere and are synthesized for various purposes, such as reports to present one's curiosity, research articles, funding proposals, academic degrees, and guidelines for professional and evidence-based practice (Fink, 2004). Thus it can be seen that literature review is not only a rephrased document, rather it draws on many different crucial academic aspects.

Apart from its central significance in academics, literature review also provides a clear framework for the paper. However, scholars face a lot of difficulties when writing literature reviews. For instance, postgraduate scholars often struggle to find their unique voice in their writing and to set up papers initially. These issues are frequently the result of an early lack of focus, a misapprehension of the purpose of their work, their contribution, and the necessity of their research. One reason is that, as Ridley (2000) points out, literature reviews can take many different forms and appear at different points in a paper. They can be early in the process, followed by more in-depth reviews that occur throughout the paper's body, or they can even direct the paper towards the end by situating it within the existent literature. Moreover, Faculty complaints often include that literature reviews are just documents that are boringly chronological, mostly describing different bits and pieces of research without proper linkage, or having insufficient structure according to the issues, and most often insufficiently informed by the hypotheses of research.

Swales' CARS Model and Ken Hyland's Metadiscourse Model Application to Literature Review Writing

John Swales' forwarded his CARS (Create a Research Space) model in 1990 in his seminal work "Genre Analysis: English in Academic and Research Settings" which provides a framework for understanding the rhetorical structure of research article introductions. His CARS model was primarily designed to analyze abstract and introduction section in research articles. However, it was later on extended by Swales and Feak (2012) to literature review section analysis and has been widely adapted to understand rhetorical organization of literature reviews. Partrick (2007) argues that literature review, like an introduction, is supposed to establish the research territory, highlight gaps or inconsistencies, and justify the need for new research. Scholars who have adapted Swales' CARS model to literature review writing argue that an effective LR should follow similar rhetorical patterns. For instance: Move 1 in Literature Reviews involves summarizing and discussing existing research to define the broader field of study. Move 2 highlights research gaps or theoretical conflicts within the reviewed studies. Move 3 presents how the current study contributes to the ongoing discourse, either by addressing a specific gap or by proposing a new perspective.

Similarly, Metadiscourse refers to the interpersonal language used by the writer to structure a conversation or perspective regarding the discourse's subject matter. It is a method of approaching language use that is predicated on the idea that, when a person write or talk, he or she is keeping an eye out for the potential responses or involvement of the audience or reader, deciding what impact they make on readers or listeners, and modifying his or her language to best serve the goals (Hyland, 2005). Thus, metadiscourse—which is a term that is frequently used in contemporary discourse analysis and language instruction—is a type of commentary on a text that is made during speaking or writing that is expressed through phrases and some words like in other words, perhaps, and for that matter etc. Metadiscourse captures the interactive nature of communication. The central idea revolves around the notion of it as discourse about another discourse. While some scholars limit this to elements which help in structuring the text as a whole, others adopt a more expansive perspective, perceiving it as the means by which authors and speakers position themselves into their discourse to convey their comprehension of both their subject matter and their readership. This relationship becomes more important when it comes to academic writing.

Ken Hyland Model of Metadiscourse

Hyland referred to his framework as the interpersonal Metadiscourse model. He argues that metadiscourse is inherently interpersonal. This is because it takes into account the reader's existing

knowledge, past reading experiences, and cognitive needs, offering writers various rhetorical strategies to connect with readers (Hyland, 2005a, p. 41). Thus, all metadiscourse markers reflect an interactional dynamic with the reader, which plays a key role in effective communication. For instance, evidential elements (e.g., "according to Z") are usually considered textual, but Hyland views them as interactive since they signify engagement with a specific academic community.

Hyland (2005a, p. 49) argues that the interactive aspect of writing relates to the writer's awareness of their audience and helps in making the text more understandable. It is so, because writers consider the readers' interests, prior knowledge, and expectations when writing the text. The extent to which a writer creates a text with the audience in mind is an important feature of the interactive dimension, which is primarily shaped by modern rhetorical principles discussed in Section 2.6.2. To elaborate, Hyland (2005a) categorizes the interactive dimension into five subtypes: transition markers, frame markers, endophoric markers, evidentials, and code glosses. According to Hyland (2005a, p. 50), transition markers help readers follow the logical and organized flow of an argument. These markers are further divided into three types: addition (furthermore, moreover etc), comparison (similarly, in contrast etc), and consequence (thus, anyway etc). Frame markers, another component of the interactive dimension, are devices that clarify the structure of a text by indicating different stages or shifts in the argument. These markers serve four main functions: (1) sequencing the text (e.g., first, next), (2) announcing the writer's goals (e.g., my purpose here is), (3) labelling text stages (e.g., in sum, to summarize), and (4) signalling topic changes (e.g., well, let's return to) (Hyland, 2005a, p. 51). Likewise, endophoric markers, which refer to specific parts of the text (Halliday & Hasan, 1976, p. 33), are used to guide readers' understanding of the writer's arguments by referencing material mentioned earlier or yet to come. For example, "see figure 2" or "as noted above" direct readers to the writer's intended interpretation (Hyland, 2005a, p. 51). Evidentials are another key element in the interactive category. These markers indicate the source of supporting information (e.g., "according to X, Z states") and help identify the writer's position within the academic discourse community (Hyland, 2005a, p. 51). Finally, code glosses provide additional clarification to ensure readers understand the writer's meaning. These markers sometimes show the writer's judgement of the readers' possible knowledge and include phrases or fragments like "this is called" or "that is" (Hyland, 2005a, p. 52).

Likewise, another broader dimension of Hyland's model is interactional dimension. It addresses how writers engage with their audience through commentary on the study under review. This dimension is designed to involve readers actively in the text and express the writer's "textual voice" or "community-recognized person" (Hyland, 2005a, p. 49). The interactional dimension includes five key subcategories: hedges, boosters, attitude markers, engagement markers, and self-mentions. Likewise, hedges are used by writers to express uncertainty and acknowledge other perspectives. They suggest that a position is open to negotiation, and that the writer's viewpoint is based on reasoning rather than absolute certainty (Hyland, 2005a, p. 52). Common hedges include words like "possible," "perhaps," and "might." In contrast, boosters express certainty and reinforce the writer's stance, often rejecting opposing viewpoints (Hyland, 2005a, p. 53). Similarly, examples of boosters include words like "clearly," "obviously," and "demonstrate." It is important to note that the balance of hedges and boosters is important for establishing regard for the reader while expressing commitment to a particular position (Hyland, 2005a, p. 53). Likewise, attitude markers are used to communicate the writer's subjective evaluation of the content, indicating the importance and relevance of information (Hyland, 2005a, p. 53). These metadiscourse markers are normally expressed by using parts of speech such as adjectives or adverbs. Similarly, self-mentions another important subcategory that involve the use of personal pronouns or possessive adjectives which explicitly signal the writer's voice and identity in the text (Hyland, 2005a, p. 53). Writers may choose to include or omit self-mentions to adopt a particular stance or reduce subjectivity. Finally, engagement markers serve to include the reader in the text's conversation, either by directly addressing them or by guiding their focus. These markers may use rhetorical devices such as questions, modal verbs, and directives (e.g., "see," "note") to direct the reader's attention and foster shared understanding (Hyland, 2005a, p. 54).

Integrated Model

The Integration of Swales' CARS model derived from his genre analysis with Hyland's metadiscourse

model offers a well-tailored model for analysis. Swales' CARS model derived from his genre theory provides context for understanding the communicative purpose and rhetorical context of literature reviews. Hyland's model functions as a tool for metadiscourse analysis, enabling detailed examination of linguistic features. The CARS foundational framework of Swales is comprehensively covered by Ken Hyland 2005 interpersonal model of metadiscourse. This integration of Swales' CARS and Hyland's metadiscourse model is helpful in comprehensive understanding of literature reviews. By combining these frameworks, researchers can contextualize metadiscourse within genre-specific conventions, examine linguistic features, and uncover how writers establish credibility, create a research niche, and engage readers. This integrated approach facilitates nuanced insights into the role of metadiscourse in academic writing, ultimately informing effective writing practices and enhancing research communication.

The following integrated Model designed for the present research works shows that both models reinforce each other. Swales' CARS model provides the structural foundation of literature review as a genre in thesis writing, whereas Ken Hyland's metadiscourse model accounts for the linguistic choices and metadiscourse composition of literature review. This integrated model sets a foundation for the exploration of a detailed examination of structural and metadiscourse strategies used by researchers in writing literature reviews.

Meta discourse Across Genre

Metadiscourse has a contextual specificity that is evident in how metadiscourse markers are utilized across different genres to facilitate interaction between the reader and the writer. It is considered as a kind of social act because it reflects the writer's social purpose, both in engaging with the reader (Kress, 1989, p. 10) and in articulating his subject matter in a specific genre (Alotaibi, 2005, p. 703). Similarly, Koutsantoni (2006, p. 24) suggests that researchers adapt their use of metadiscourse based on their relationship with readers of the genre to better control their argument. Consequently, the use of metadiscourse varies across genres depending on factors like (1) the intended audience, (2) the purpose of the text, and (3) the social context (Hyland, 2005a, p. 87). Amiryousefi and Rasekh (2010, p. 161) note that texts are categorized into specific genres based on recurring linguistic or rhetorical features, including metadiscourse.

Before examining metadiscourse research in various genres, it is crucial to define the concept of genre. Hyland (2005a, p. 87) describes genre as a collection of texts that represent typical ways in which writers use language to respond to specific, recurring situations. Miller (1984, p. 159) defines genre as "typified rhetorical actions based in recurrent situations." The essence of genre lies in its function as a form of social action (Martin, 1985), where members of a particular community recognize patterns in the discourse they use, giving them an advantage in both writing and interpreting texts (Swales, 1990, p. 63). The primary rationale for this is that writing is a practice shaped by writers' anticipation of reader expectations (Hyland, 2005a, p. 87). These expectations are informed by previous texts of a similar type that writers have read. Hyland (2005a) further explains that particular choices are familiar in specific contexts, and through repeated use of these choices, they come to represent conventionalized forms that enable communities to form and ideas to be exchanged. Thus, every successful text reflects not only the writer's awareness of the context but also the writer understands of the reader, who is an integral part of that context (Swales, 1990, p. 62).

Academic Writing Sub-Genre: Research Articles, Essays, Dissertations

Since different genres exhibit varying uses of metadiscourse, as evidenced by the distinctions between newspapers and academic writing (Lee, 2009), Academic writing tends to feature more interactive markers than interactional ones overall, since it emphasizes the organization of the text more than engaging with readers or addressing potential objections (Alshahrani, 2015; Zakaria & Malik, 2018). Hyland (2005) in his analysis of academic writing found that students frequently used interactive markers. In these interactive markers hedges and evidentials were the most used subcategories. The excess use of these subcategories shows the importance of presenting claims and supporting them with evidence to convince readers. Moreover, attitude markers are among the least commonly used in academic writing (Lee, 2009, p. 172; Abdual Ameer et al., 2018, p. 356). In other words, it suggests that students are less likely to engage emotionally to convince their readers.

Among various other genres, academic writing is a major genre in the English language (Biber et al.,

1999), that encompass a variety of sub-genres, such as research articles, essays, and dissertations. Although these sub-genres fall under the broader category of academic writing, they each use metadiscourse differently. Research articles, for example, are typically written by experts, while essays and dissertations are often produced by students, who are generally considered novice writers (Lee, 2009). A brief comparison of how metadiscourse is applied across these sub-genres will follow, with a particular focus on dissertations, as this research investigates this specific genre.

Metadiscourse in Thesis and Research Writing

This metadiscourse is in every genre of academic writing. Like it is widely used in the reviews of academic book (Tse & Hyland, 2006), in undergraduate thesis reports (Hyland, 2010a), similarly in postgraduate research thesis (Hyland, 2004). For instance, frequency counts indicate that in a corpus of four million MPhil level postgraduate theses, there is roughly one signal per 21 words (Hyland, 2004), with hedges and transitions being the most often used devices. Overall, comparable distributions in published academic writing are reflected in this use of metadiscourse to articulate arguments cautiously and explicitly (Hyland, 1998b & 2005). This use can vary from discipline to discipline. In another corpus PhD dissertations were subjected to metadiscourse analysis. The PhD dissertations had nearly twice as many interactive forms. This may be attributed in part to the lengthier PhD theses, requiring more interactive tools to organise complex arguments. However, it may also reflect a more thoughtful understanding of the audience, text, and self. Applications differ throughout fields as well; in social science disciplines, more hedges, attitude indicators, and self-mention, as well as more metadiscourse in general were used. Naturally, these applications highlight the larger importance that overt subjective interpretations play in disciplines like that of social sciences and humanities, where authors are required to put in more effort to establish rapport with readers persuading and helping them of interpretations.

In line with the above discussion, Tse and Hyland (2006), and (2010a) have applied metadiscourse model to book reviews, undergraduate research reports, graduate theses, and PhD dissertation. Similarly Shafique et al, (2019) conducted a metadiscourse analysis of research articles written by native English versus Pakistani researchers. They used Hyland and Tsse (2004) model of metadiscourse. Using the metadiscourse approach proposed by Hyland and Tse (2004a), total of 100 research articles by both native English, and Pakistani ESL scholars were selected for this study. This study used a mixed method research technique that is corpus-based metadiscourse analysis. The data was first quantified using a corpus-based method Antconc 3.2.4w 2011, and then each metadiscursive tool was subjected to a qualitative analysis. The metadiscourse markers used by native speaker researchers were 17778, whereas the metadiscourse markers used by Pakistani researcher were 16162. Overall, the findings reported that the native English academic authors utilized more interactional markers, whereas Pakistani research writers used more interactive markers. The overall findings showed that native English researchers are more compelling because they skillfully direct readers through the text and include them through a variety of interactional metadiscourse markers.

The above studies indicate metadiscourse use in numerous frequencies across different levels of study in different discipline; however, they did not touch upon the crucial section of literature review chapter especially in MPhil Linguistics theses. The present research will do metadiscourse analysis of literature review part in MPhil English linguistics theses to provide a more detailed picture of the metadiscourse used in the theses of this discipline. Before proceeding into that, it is important to state some empirical studies done on literature review section in different parts of the world using different research method. This will help in creating a detailed picture of research on literature review, and will provide a research gap as well.

Rationale for Using Swales' CARS and Hyland's Metadiscourse Model

Swales' CARS model and Hyland's (2005) metadiscourse model both play important roles in structuring and analyzing academic writing, particularly in literature reviews. Swales' CARS model outlines three key moves: (Move 1) establishing a research territory, (Move 2) identifying a niche/gap in the existing literature and (Move 3) presenting the current research as a solution (Swales, 1990). All these moves are important in structuring a literature review which enables the researchers to frame the research context, identify shortcomings, and establish the relevance of their own research work. Therefore,

CARS framework guides researchers to address gaps in literature while clearly positioning their research within a broader academic context.

On the other hand, Hyland’s metadiscourse model contributes to it by focusing on how writers guide and engage readers through the text using language (Hyland, 2005). For that matter, Interactive metadiscourse markers like frame markers, code glosses, transitions and evidentials help structure the review and present prior research, while interactional metadiscourse markers like hedges and self-mentions allow authors to position their claims, express tentativeness, and establish authority (Hyland, 2005). The present research therefore uses an integrated approach comprising these two models. This model will help in comprehensive analysis of literature review by providing both a structural framework (CARS), and a tool for managing the researcher's interaction with the reader (Hyland, 2005). This combination will ensure that the review is both logically organized and effectively communicated.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, specifically a convergent parallel design, to examine metadiscourse in literature review sections of MPhil English Linguistics theses. Grounded in an integrated framework combining Swales’ CARS model and Hyland’s metadiscourse model, the research draws on secondary data from seven purposively selected theses submitted between 2020 and 2024 at Islamia College University Peshawar. The analysis proceeds in two phases: a qualitative textual analysis to identify interactive and interactional metadiscourse features within the structural moves of literature reviews, followed by a quantitative phase in which these features are manually counted and distributed across moves and steps. Data were coded deductively using predefined categories adapted from Hyland, with flexibility to refine codes where necessary. To ensure consistency and credibility, inter-coder reliability was established through independent coding and subsequent agreement among trained researchers. This combined approach enables a systematic yet nuanced understanding of how metadiscourse functions within genre-specific conventions to shape coherence, authorial stance, and reader engagement.

Description of Codes

In research practices the data is most often codified provided that that it makes the research systematic and organized, because a non-codified data often makes the analysis vague and disorganized (Charmaz 2014). The data was therefore codified as per integrated model to make the analysis systematic and organized. The coding scheme was adapted from Hyland (2010). Following is the table of codes and their abbreviations that would be used throughout in findings and discussion respectively.

Ken Hyland’s Metadiscourse Model 2005

Category	Subcategory	Code
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Interactive Markers

IA	Transition	IA-1
	Frame Markers	IA-2
	Endophoric	IA-3
	Evidentials	IA-4
	Code Glosses	IA-5

Interactional Markers

IR	Hedges	IR-1
	Boosters	IR-2
	Attitude	IR-3
	Engagement Markers	IR-4
	Self Mention	IR-5

Swales CARS Model 1990

Category	Subcategory	Code
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Move 1 Establishing Centrality

- M1 Establishing centrality S1
- Making topic generalization, or S2
- Reviewing previous studies S3

Move 2 Establishing a Niche

- M2 Counter claiming S1
- Indicating a gap S2
- Question arising

Continuing Tradition S3

Move 3 Occupying the Niche

- M3 Outlining purpose or Announcing present research S1
- Announcing principle findings S2
- Indicating RA Structure (N/A) S3

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This study analyzed metadiscourse markers in literature review section of MPhil English Linguistics theses using Swales' CARS model and Hyland's (2005) framework of metadiscourse. Total seven samples were analyzed. The findings from the seven analyzed samples indicated variations in the use of interactive and interactional markers across different literature reviews. Different interactive and interactional categories such as evidentials, transitions, boosters, hedges, frame markers, engagement markers, and self-mentions were examined to determine their role in structuring discourse and engaging readers. Additionally, Swales' CARS model was applied to investigate the effectiveness of Moves 1, 2, and 3 in structuring literature reviews.

Interactive Metadiscourse Markers

Hyland's model of metadiscourse has two main categories. One is interactive and the other is interactional. The interactive markers contain further five sub categories that are IA-1, IA-2, IA-3, IA-4, and IA-5. It is important to discuss the prevalence and usage of interactive metadiscourse markers across the analyzed samples.

5.2.1. Transitions (IA-1)

Among the interactive markers, IA-1 was notably frequent in samples by A (38), B (29), and D (27). The code functions to bring coherence and connect ideas or sentences or paragraphs to facilitation logical progression. Moreover, the under usage of IA-1 was observed in F (26), E (24), with the lowest rate of only 22 in sample G. This under utilization is suggestive of a less structured flow of arguments in the relevant literature review samples. The findings of this study is consistent with Hyland & Tse (2004, 2006), Alharbi (2021), and Shafique et al. (2019). The study by Shafique et al. (2019) is more contextually related to the current findings, where they, in their comparative analysis of metadiscourse usage on native English versus Pakistani ESL researchers found that Pakistani researchers used more interactive markers (transitions, evidentials) but fewer interactional markers (hedges, boosters, engagement markers).

Frame Markers (IA-2)

The use of IA-2 was most prominently used by sample C 66 which shows that the author has a highly structured approach. Moreover, sample D and A also used significant frame markers of 40 and 37 respectively which demonstrate structured discourse. In sample B and E we have a moderate number of IA-2 with 36 and 30 respectively. On contrary, sample F and G had the least IA-2 of 13 and 10 respectively. Their samples suggest that they relied more on implicit structuring than explicit signposting. This aligns with previous research indicating that strong structuring devices, such as

‘firstly,’ ‘finally,’ and ‘in conclusion,’ help organize arguments systematically (Swales, 1990).

Endophoric Markers (IA-3)

IA-3 use was demonstrated the highest in sample C 24 that indicated a well-structured writing. Similarly, sample A has 5 and sample B has 2 showed moderate usages with some internal references but not consistently across the whole sample. On the other hand, sample F completely lacked endophoric markers. Sample G has 2 and sample D has 3 IA-3 which indicate that their texts lacked clear connections between literature discussions and findings. Moreover, sample E had slightly better integration of 8 IA-3 compared to others but still fell short of the expected standard for well-structured academic writing. These findings partially contrast with Qian and Krugly-Smolka (2008), who noted that non-native English writers often overuse endophoric markers in to enhance textual cohesion in their literature reviews

Evidentials (IA-4)

Among the analyzed samples, the high presence of IA-4 was noted as 52 in sample B, followed by 51 in sample A, and 47 in sample D. In sample B there was overreliance on prior research and less critical reflection of these evidentials. However, the lowest was recorded as 15 in sample C, followed by 18 in sample F and 20 in sample G. The use of IA-4 indicated that more than half of the samples relied more on empirical validation of claims, a feature widely endorsed in academic writing also found by Shafique et al. (2019).

5.2.5. Code Glosses (IA-5)

As far as the usage of IA-5 is considered, it was extensively used as 109 in sample C followed by 97 in sample A. This extensive utilization has brought more conceptual clarity and elaboration of key ideas but at the cost of low evidentials. Similarly, Sample D reflected 85 whereas sample E revealed 78 code glosses. However, Sample F (30), B (40) has relatively low IA-4 as 30 and 40 respectively. However, sample G exhibited minimal use of only 25, which indicates an assumption of prior reader knowledge and less emphasis on explanation. This aligns with Hyland’s (2005) observation that code glosses improve reader engagement by explicitly defining and illustrating abstract concepts.

Interactional Metadiscourse Markers

After discussing the interactive metadiscourse markers in the analyzed samples, it is important to discuss Interactional metadiscourse which is another broader category in Hyland’s model that is further subcategorised in five subcategories IR-1, IR-2, IR-3, IR-4, IR-5.

Hedges (IR-1)

Among the analyzed samples IR-1 sample A was having highest as 69, followed by sample D 56, and then by sample B as 50. These samples demonstrated a more cautious and informed approach in making claims. Moreover, Sample C and E have moderate IA-4 of 48 and 41 respectively which balances certainty with caution. However sample F and G in contrast, demonstrated hedging of 1 and 9 only which resulted in a more assertive, but less flexible argumentation style. This aligns with prior research (Hyland, 1996; Salager-Meyer, 1994) that hedging enhances academic credibility by acknowledging alternative viewpoints.

Boosters (IR-2)

In the discussion on IR-2 among the samples, sample C, D, and A used the highest number of boosters as 97, 73, and 70 respectively. The extensive use of IR-2 in these samples shows a strong commitment to claims made on key concepts and trends. Moreover, sample E and B also showed assertive argumentation by using IR-2 in proportion of 62 and 55. Contrary to it, sample F and G demonstrated the lowest booster usage as 26 and 30 which suggest a less forceful argumentative approach. The use of boosters aligns with Hyland’s (2005) findings that confident academic writing tends to employ strong assertions.

Attitude Markers (IR-3)

If we look at IR-3 across all the samples, it is evident that Sample C, D, and A used the most IR-3 as 33, 20, and 14 respectively these three literature review samples are aptly evaluated. Moreover, sample B and E also reflected some subjectivity in their writing with IR-3 as 18 and 15. Conversely, sample F

and G used the least of 11 and 9 IR-3 which suggests a more neutral or detached writing style. This supports research by Hyland (2005), which found that academic texts often reflect authorial perspectives through evaluative language.

Engagement Markers (IR-4)

In the context of IR-4 across the samples, sample C showed the highest use of engagement markers (IR-4) as 22, directly addressing the reader and facilitates interaction between the writer and readers. Moreover, sample D, E, and B also demonstrated moderate IR-4 as 17, 15, and 14 respectively. In contrast to these samples, sample A, F, and G used the least IR-4 as 12, 11, and 10 respectively. These three samples therefore have weak writer-reader bond and indicates less explicit reader interaction. This supports findings by Hyland (2005) that engagement markers make academic texts more dialogic and inclusive.

Self-Mention (IR-5)

As far as this important category of interactional metadiscourse is concerned, among all the samples, the use of self-mentions IR-5 was highest only in sample E as 14 which indicated a personal, subjective, and reflective writing style with a strong sense of locating herself in her research work. Moreover, Sample A and B have utilized the same number of IR-5 as 3. Similarly sample D has used IR-5 only once whereas Sample F and G have not used IR-4 at all, and have therefore completely avoided self-mentions, suggesting a preference for impersonal discourse structures.

Table

The following table contains the total number of sample analyzed and the use of interactive and interactional metadiscourse marker across each sample.

SAMPLE	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
INTERACTIVE							
IA-1	38	29	26	27	24	26	18
IA-2	37	36	66	33	8	13	12
IA-3	5	2	24	3	7	0	3
IA-4	51	52	15	42	43	18	38
IA-5	97	40	109	20	60	30	16
INTERACTIONAL							
IR-1	69	11	14	26	19	1	9
IR-2	70	47	97	73	62	26	40
IR-3	14	18	33	20	9	11	14
IR-4	12	11	22	11	13	13	3
IR-5	3	3	0	1	14	0	0

Now if we look at the use of metadiscourse markers at interactive and interactional level, it is evident that IA-5 is extensively utilized followed by IA-4 and IA-2 respectively. It shows that the researchers tend to clarify concepts and provide evidences and references from the previous studies, but with limited critical reflection on them. Hyland (2005) also noted that ESL writers tend to rely on IA-4 rather than presenting strong personal arguments, which is observed in the current research. Contrastively, in interactional markers, IR-2 is extensively utilized followed by IR-1, whereas IR-5 is the least used code across all the samples which shows that there is more focus on description and summarization with a weak reader involvement and critical engagement on part of the researcher

Graph

The following graph contains the total number of interactive and interactional metadiscourse markers

across all the seven samples. Collectively, the number of interactive markers are greater i.e. 1068 than interactional metadiscourse markers which are 789 across the entire seven sample. In other words, there is more reliance on description whereas, critical reflection on part of the researchers is relatively limited. These findings are consistent with Alshahrani (2015) who found that researchers in theses and dissertations favours interactive metadiscourse over interactional metadiscourse, similar to the findings of this research where interactive markers are more utilized than interactional markers.

Graph 1: Comparison of Interactive and Interactional MDM across Samples

Discussion on Swales' CARS Model

This section provides a thorough discussion on the rhetorical organization of the analyzed literature reviews samples as per Swales' CARS (1990) model. The prevalence of each move and step across the samples is discussed in a proper order.

Move 1: Establishing a Territory

Move 1 in Swales' CARS model is actually named as "establishing a research territory" which situates the research within a broader academic context. It further consists of three steps that are: "Claiming centrality, Making topic generalization, and reviewing items of previous research studies." All the seven samples under analysis have followed move 1 and steps of CARS model. However sample E has no step 3 in move 1. As far as the metadiscourse markers use in this move is concerned, IA-1, IA-4, IR-3, and IR-4 were used in excess as compared to other markers. Moreover, IA-1 was extensively present in sample A, B and D which made their arguments properly connected in establishing a research territory. However, F and G had fewer IA-1, with a weaker textual cohesion, which aligns with Alharbi (2021), who reported that students often underuse transitions in poorly structured research texts. As one of the step 3 in move 1 related to reviewing of previous research that demands the proper use of IA-4 to cite previous research for justification of statements and claims. In this connection IA-4 was most frequent in sample A, B, and D where enough scholarly references were provided to claims, methods, and works used in literature reviews. This is consistent with Hyland (2005), who found evidentials to be a core feature of academic writing, particularly in theses. However sample F and G had lower counts, supporting Akindede (2008), who found that graduate students often struggle with referencing prior studies effectively. Moreover, IR-3 were more frequent in sample C, D, and A as attitude marker to show the significance of their research. Moreover, it is important to note that IR-4 were relatively low across samples in this move with low critical engagement being consistent with Shafique et al. (2019), who found that Pakistani ESL researchers underuse engagement markers in research report writing.

Move 2: Establishing a Niche

Move 2 of CARS model is about establishing a Niche. It further has sub steps comprising: "counter claiming, indicating a research gap, question raising/continuing the tradition." In analysis of move 2, IA-2 were highly present in sample C, D, and A, effectively structuring problem statements. This aligns with Swales (1990, 2012), who emphasized the importance of frame markers in guiding academic arguments. In contrast, G and F had fewer markers, making their niche establishment less explicit, which supports Nelson & Amayah (2010), who reported similar challenges in students' ability to define research gaps. Likewise, IR-1, used for cautious claims, was more prevalent in sample A, D, and B, which shows a proper argumentation style. Moreover, sample G and F lacked sufficient hedging, which aligns with Shafique et al. (2019), who found that Pakistani researchers tend to underuse hedging compared to native English researchers. Likewise, IR-4 was highest in sample C and D, demonstrating an interactive tone when discussing research problems.

Move 3: Occupying the Niche

Move 3 of CARS model refers to occupying the research Niche comprising three steps: outlining purpose or announcing a present research, announcing principle findings, and structure of research article (primarily of RA and introduction). However, this is specifically for structuring abstract and introduction, it is therefore rarely followed in the present research because this research focused on analyzing literature review section only. Among the seven sample, only sample A and D had fully reflected on each step of the move. However, Sample B, C, E, G, had followed only two steps of the move, whereas sample G had not followed the move altogether. It actually justifies the study's contributions.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, this case study analyzed metadiscourse markers in the literature review section of MPhil English Linguistics theses of Islamia College Peshawar using Swales' CARS and Hyland's (2005) metadiscourse framework. The findings indicated significant variation in the use of interactive and interactional metadiscourse markers across the seven samples. Among interactive markers, IA-1 was frequently employed in samples A, B, and D, that ensured logical flow, while F and G underutilized them, which made their argumentation relatively less structured. Moreover, IA-2 was most prominent in sample C, showing strong discourse organization, whereas F and G were having a relatively poor structural organization. Similarly, IA-4 was extensively used in samples A, B, and D, which provided citations and empirical validation for the works and concepts cited. Likewise, IA-5 was highest in sample C and A, which contributed to conceptual clarity, but at the cost of fewer evidentials.

In terms of interactional markers, the use of IR-1 was dominant in samples A, D, and B, which reflected a cautious and critically informed academic writing, whereas F and G lacked hedging leading to more assertive but rigid argumentation. Similarly, IR-2 was prominent in samples C, D, and A, which showed a strong authorial stance. However, F and G demonstrated minimal booster usage which suggested a less assertive argumentative style. Similarly, IR-3 was most visible in C, D, and A, with a strong subjective stance, while sample F and G maintained a neutral perspective. Moreover, IR-4 was highest in sample C, D, and E, which facilitates reader engagement, while samples F and G had the weakest writer-reader interaction. Finally, IR-5 was only significant in sample E, while others samples especially C, F, and G, completely avoided self-mentioning in the research with lead to an impersonal writing style.

From a structural perspective, the Swales' CARS model showed that move 1 which is establishing a Territory was effectively followed across all samples, but sample E lacked Step 3. Moreover, move 2 which is establishing a niche was followed in samples C, D, and A, with appropriate frame markers and hedges, whereas samples F and G had weaker niche establishment. However, move 3as occupying the niche was inconsistently applied, with A and D being the only samples fully reflecting its steps. The findings of this study aligns with previous studies, including Hyland (2005), Swales (1990), and Shafique et al. (2019), confirming that Pakistani ESL researchers rely more on interactive metadiscourse markers particularly IA-1, IA-4 and IA-2 than interactional markers (IR-1, IR-4, IR-5). The underuse of engagement markers and hedging aligns with Akindele (2008) and Shafique et al. (2019), who noted similar patterns in Pakistani academic writing.

Suggestions based on Findings

The findings of this study indicated several areas where the use of metadiscourse markers in MPhil English Linguistics theses can be improved to enhance academic writing clarity, coherence, and engagement.

- One key area for improvement is the use of IR-4 which was underutilized in most samples. Academic writers should incorporate rhetorical questions, direct addresses, and inclusive language to foster reader interaction and engagement.
- Another important consideration is the balance IR-1 and IR-2 in academic writing. Some samples demonstrated an overuse of boosters, making their arguments overly assertive, while others lacked sufficient hedging which has made the claims appear absolute. A balanced use of these markers would enhance both the credibility and persuasiveness of writing.
- Another significant finding was the underuse of IR-5 in most samples, which made the writing impersonal and detached. Research scholars may use a balanced IR-5 to effectively locate themselves in their work.
- Moreover text organization was also inconsistent across samples, particularly in the use of IA-2 and IA-1. Writers should make a more deliberate effort to incorporate explicit structuring devices to ensure clarity in their writing.
- The study also revealed inconsistencies in the IA-4 across different samples. Some relied excessively on citations without integrating them into a critical discussion, while others lacked

sufficient empirical support. Writers should aim for a balanced use of evidentials to cite multiple sources rather than merely listing them.

- Similarly, IA-5 was more frequent in some samples than others, affecting conceptual clarity.
- One of the major structural weaknesses observed in some samples was in Move 2 (Establishing a Niche) of Swales' CARS model, which was often underdeveloped. Literature reviews should clearly identify gaps in prior research, unresolved debates, or critical questions that justify the study's significance.

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